

Detection of Avian Poxvirus in an Egyptian goose (*Alopochen aegyptiacus*)

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Abstract

Pathological and immunohistochemical findings in the skin of an Egyptian goose naturally infected with avian poxvirus are described in this paper. Cutaneous papules and nodules were observed on the unfeathered parts of the skin. Histopathological examination revealed hyperplasia of the epithelial cells of the *stratum spinosum*, with presence of eosinophilic intracytoplasmic inclusions. Avipoxvirus was detected in the formalin fixed paraffin embedded tissues of goose skin by immunoperoxidase and immunofluorescence. To our knowledge, this could be the first record of avian pox in geese in Egypt.

Key Words: Geese pox, Histopathology, Immunohistochemistry, *Alopochen aegyptiacus*.

Introduction

Avian poxviruses (APVs) are members of the genus *Avipoxvirus* within the subfamily *Chordopoxvirinae* in the family *Poxviridae*. They are large DNA viruses, which were found worldwide (Bolte *et al.*, 1999), and occur particularly in tropical and sub-tropical countries (Reed and Schrader, 1989; Yoshikawa and Alam, 2002). They are the causative agents of acute contagious disease in domestic and wild birds characterized by proliferative skin lesions as well as fibrous necrotic proliferative lesions on the mucous membrane of the oral cavity, oesophagus and upper section of the respiratory tract (Tripathy and Reed, 2003). Currently, only ten avipoxvirus species are listed under the genus *Avipoxvirus* (Moyer *et al.*, 2000; Fauquet *et al.*, 2005).

Waterfowl is not considered a major reservoir or vector for this disease; however experimental infection of domestic ducks and domestic geese by fowl poxvirus has been documented (Kirmse, 1967). Natural avian pox infection is most commonly known in domestic fowl, where the disease can reach levels of economic importance (Bruner and Giliespie, 1973). The natural infection of

avipox in a Canadian goose was considered a record (Cox, 1980). An avian poxvirus from cutaneous lesions in a Hawaiian goose was characterized in the study of Kim and Tripathy, (2006). To our knowledge, there are no published records of avian pox among aquatic birds in Egypt. The purpose of this paper is to report a case of naturally occurring pox infection in Egyptian goose (*Alopochen aegyptiacus*).

Materials and methods

Case history. In August, 2010, a mature Egyptian goose was found in emaciated condition and presented to Pathology Department, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Zagazig University, Egypt.

Histopathology. Samples were collected from skin lesions of the submitted goose. The tissue samples were fixed in 10% buffered formalin, embedded in paraffin, sectioned at 4 µm and stained with haematoxylin and eosin.

Immunohistochemistry.

Immunohistochemical analysis for detection of avian poxvirus in formalin fixed paraffin embedded tissues of the affected goose skin was performed using immunoperoxidase and immunofluorescence.

Immunoperoxidase. The tissue specimens were stained using an indirect immunoperoxidase technique. The sections were deparaffinized, treated with proteinase K at 37°C for 15 min for retrieval of antigen then incubated with primary polyclonal antibodies against fowlpox virus (Department of Avian and Rabbit Medicine, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Zagazig University, Egypt) for 60 min. The sections were incubated with horseradish peroxidase conjugated with goat anti-chicken IgG (KPL, USA) at a concentration of 1/200 in PBS for 30 min then washed with PBS. Immunostaining was obtained using 3-Amino-9-Ethylcarbazol substrate for 12 min at room temperature in the dark. Sections were counterstained with haematoxylin and examined under microscope for detection of poxvirus antigen in goose tissues. The primary antibodies were omitted and replaced by PBS for negative controls.

Immunofluorescence. The sections were deparaffinized, treated with 0.1% Triton X-100 for 3 min at room temp then incubated with primary polyclonal antibodies against fowlpox virus for 30 min and washed with PBS. They were incubated with anti-chicken IgG (whole molecule) FITC conjugate (Sigma) for 30 min and washed with PBS. Tissues were covered, dried and examined for specific positive intracytoplasmic greenish yellow color using Fluorescent microscope (Leica).

Results and discussion

Although avian pox is endemic in Egypt particularly among chickens, turkey and pigeons (El-Sabbach, 1962; Metwally, 1994; Eid *et al.*, 1998), there are no available records on the disease in aquatic birds in Egypt. The emergence of avian pox in Egyptian goose examined in the current study could be the first record of avian pox in aquatic birds in Egypt. This paper describes pathological and immunohistochemical

findings in the skin of Egyptian goose naturally infected with pox virus.

Grossly, the goose was emaciated and showed cutaneous lesions mainly; papules and nodules on the unfeathered parts of the head and neck. Histologically, the epithelial cells of the skin and feather follicles revealed acanthosis, ballooning degeneration of the keratinocytes, and large eosinophilic cytoplasmic inclusion bodies (Bollinger's bodies) (Figure 1). These inclusions appeared as masses or large eosinophilic granules distended the cytoplasm with complete absence of the nucleus. The feather shafts were degenerated and necrotic with perifollicular lymphocytic and few heterophilic infiltrates. The musculatures of the subcutaneous tissue showed partial hyalinization, oedema and lymphocytic infiltrations. These findings were similar to those in the previously described case of natural avipoxvirus infection in a Canadian goose (Cox, 1980) and other avian species (Minbay and Kreier, 1973; Hernandez *et al.*, 2001; Gülbahar *et al.*, 2005). Previously it was reported that as inclusion bodies increased in size the epithelial cells distended, resulting in degeneration and necrosis of the cells. It might be the result of viral propagation in the cells (Tanizaki *et al.*, 1987; Tripathy and Reed, 2003).

Figure 1: Skin section of goose stained with H&E

Skin section of goose stained with H&E showing large intracytoplasmic eosinophilic inclusions within degenerated epithelial cells of skin. X1200.

The presence of avian poxvirus was confirmed by immunohistochemical assay in

the hyperplastic epithelial cells. Immunolocalization of pox virus antigen was seen as granular brown coloring in the cytoplasm of the infected cells, inclusion bodies, and necrotic and desquamated cells in the *stratum corneum* of the skin (Figure 2). The use of indirect IF technique on formalin fixed paraffin embedded tissues of affected skin revealed intracytoplasmic greenish yellow coloration in the infected cells (Figure 3). The present study found that immunostaining of viral antigen in the skin occurred mainly within the cytoplasm of hyperplastic epithelial cells with cytoplasmic inclusion bodies. These findings are consistent with previous observations in chicken and quails (Gülbahar *et al.*, 2005; Beytut and Haligür, 2007).

Figure 2: Skin section of goose stained with immunoperoxidase

Skin section of goose stained with immunoperoxidase showing positive immunoreaction of hyperplastic epithelial cells with inclusion bodies for avipoxvirus antibodies. Immunoreactivity using 3-Amino-9-Ethylcarbazole. Counterstained with haematoxylin

Figure 3: Skin section of goose stained with immunofluorescence

Skin section of goose stained with immunofluorescence showing intracytoplasmic greenish yellow fluorescence.

In conclusion, histopathological findings, along with gross cutaneous lesions, indicated a poxvirus infection in Egyptian goose (*Alopochen aegyptiacus*). However, the presence of the typical skin lesions is not sufficient to definitively diagnose avian poxvirus infection because nutritional deficiencies, mycotoxins, and other agents, such as papilloma virus could produce similar lesions (Smits *et al.*, 2005). Consequently, even though epithelial hyperplasia and Bollinger bodies are histologically indicative of an avian poxvirus infection, immunohistochemistry should be applied to ensure a reliable diagnosis of the disease. The detection of avian pox in an Egyptian goose is potential for i) further follow up the virus in backyard aquatic birds. ii) Studying the relatedness to other common pox viruses.

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